

BIOLOGICAL INVESTIGATION OF ASTRAGALUS ROOT POWDER IN THE MANAGEMENT OF LIVER ENZYMES IN NONALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER HUMAN PATIENTS A RANDOMIZED CONTROL TRAIL

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14928490>

Keywords

Astragalus root powder, (Astragalus membranaceus), liver function enzyme, nonalcoholic fatty liver, hepatoprotective

Article History

Received on 18 January 2025

Accepted on 18 February 2025

Published on 26 February 2025

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Abstract

Globally, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is becoming the most common chronic liver disease. NAFLD is thought to be the hepatic marker of metabolic syndrome, which is frequently linked to metabolic risk factors such as diabetes, obesity, hypertension, and hyperlipidemia. The medicinal properties of Astragalus root powder, which is made from the Astragalus plant, are widely recognized. For thousands of years, traditional Chinese medicine has utilized it to boost vitality, fortify the immune system, and enhance general health. Astragalus root powder is high in antioxidants and anti-inflammatory substances, and it is thought to protect against a variety of ailments, improve heart health, and promote healthy ageing. It may also help manage illnesses such as diabetes by balancing blood sugar levels and improving the body's natural defense mechanism. This study aims to assess the chemical, phytochemical, and mineral profiles of Astragalus root powder, as well as its hepatoprotective capabilities. The findings revealed that the raw material was significant in all aspects of its initial analysis for future use in the study. Significant results were obtained from the antioxidant profile, which comprised ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP), 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) scavenging activity, total flavonoid content (TFC), and total phenolic content (TPC). Measurements of aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), creatinine, and bilirubin levels were then used to assess the hepatoprotective effect in the experimental groups G1 and G2, which were given dosages of 3g and 6g/day, respectively, and the control group G0, which was not receiving any treatment. The effects of Astragalus root powder on liver enzymes and associated markers were studied before and after two months. The findings revealed that a 6g/day intake of Astragalus root powder for 60 days has highly significant hepatoprotective effects against non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) without any adverse effects.

INTRODUCTION

People who drink little or no alcohol may develop Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD), a condition in which the liver becomes too fat. With almost 30.1% of the population affected, it is the most prevalent type of chronic liver disease in the globe. (R. Loomba, 2021).

Non-alcoholic fatty liver (NAFL) is caused by steatosis, which is defined as an excess buildup of fat (in the form of triglycerides) in hepatocytes (>5% fat content in the liver) (Brunt, E.M., 2015). Elevated liver enzymes, such as alanine amino transferase (ALT) and aspartate amino transferase (AST) (Shamsoddini, A., 2015), as well as an accumulation of excess fat in the liver cells (hepatocytes), are characteristics of nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD). The elevated fats are in the form of triglycerides and cholesterol. If the fat content is greater than 5% in liver than this condition is referred as nonalcoholic fatty liver (NAFL) NAFLD can advance through various phases, beginning with simple fatty liver (steatosis), which is typically benign. However, it can progress to nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), which causes inflammation and liver cell damage. (Orci LA, et al., 2016). Persistent inflammation can cause fibrosis, or scar tissue formation around the liver, and eventually cirrhosis, a severe and irreversible disorder. In its most advanced stages, NAFLD can lead to liver failure and an increased risk of liver cancer. (Hannah Jr WN, et al., 2016) Weight loss, a nutritious diet, and regular exercise are common lifestyle changes used to treat NAFLD. Early detection and treatments are critical to prevent the disease's progression and accompanying complications. (Corey KE, and Rinella ME., 2016)

For thousands of years, Chinese herbs have been utilized in China as a traditional treatment to increase human immunity (Yin et al., 2009; Shahrajabian et al., 2018). According to Li et al. (2011), astragalus is said to assist pass water and improve Qi. Wei Zheng, a term indicating skeletal muscle tiredness and atrophy, has been treated with it (Zhou and Mei, 2014). One of the most well-liked herbal remedies for health promotion that has been utilized for more than 2000 years in China is the dried root of *A. membranous*, which was originally recorded in Shennong Bencao Jing.

In numerous models of oxidative stress-related diseases, constituents of dried *Astragalus* spp. roots offer substantial protection against damage to the heart, brain, kidney, intestine, liver, and lungs. They are also a significant component of traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) and are currently used extensively as immune modulators, particularly to support immune health for a variety of chronic degenerative diseases. *Astragalus radix* has recently shown promise as an adjuvant cancer treatment medication (Wang et al., 2003).

Since it has been established that many natural medications are safer than synthetic ones, patients have recently shown a strong interest in using natural plants and herbs as medicines. *Astragalus*, or *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. (Fabaceae), is a plant that is utilized both medicinally and as food (Gomaa, A.A, 2021). The extracts of *Astragalus* have proved anti-hypercholesterolemia activity that was indicated by reduced low-density lipoprotein (LDL) oxidation and lower triglycerides and cholesterol. Several studies showed that dietary consumption of *Astragalus* extract may act as an antioxidant agent against cardiovascular disease in hypercholesterolemic patients (Fogelman, Y., 2016). The present study was conducted to evaluate the hepatoprotective efficacy of *Astragalus* in the NAFLD patients.

Many medicinal products are regarded the primary treatment for hyperlipidemia, but they also have adverse effects that might lead to other health problems, such as statins causing liver damage. As a result, a non-toxic, safe, and effective technique of preventing and controlling hyperlipidaemia is preferable. For this reason, natural food elements that can reduce hazards while also treating the condition must be researched.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of raw material

Astragalus roots were purchased from the market and water-washed. Roots shade-dried, crushed and filtered to collect a grainy powder and filled in polythene bags to avoid any contamination (Ali, A.F., 2021).

Initial preliminary Characterization of Astragalus root powder

Astragalus root powder was subjected to analyzed various assays for further usage

Proximate profile to analyze the chemical and nutritional components of astragalus root powder

Astragalus root powder was assessed for moisture, ash, crude, fat, protein, crude fiber and nitrogen extract as done by according to their standard procedures using AOAC (2012) techniques (Heleno, S.A, 2015).

Determination of minerals

Suitable minerals analysis of Astragalus root powder such Na, Mg, K, Ca, iron and zinc was analyzed by specific protocols and by using spectrophotometry (Ghafoor, A., 2022).

Phytochemical and antioxidants characteristics of Astragalus root powder

The total phenolic content (TPC) and total flavonoid content (TFC) of Astragalus root powder were determined by phytochemical analysis. The colorimetric method published by Zhou (2019) was used to determine TFC, whereas DPPH and FRAP were determined by Zhou.

Therapeutic capacity of Astragalus root powder to check its hepatoprotective potential

To evaluate the hepatoprotective effects of Astragalus root powder on liver enzyme improvement, the following criteria were observed for the inclusion of patients in the study. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring that they were not coerced or pressured to participate.

Selection of patients

NAFLD female patient with their labs of age 30-45 years were selected from the General Outpatient Department of Civil Hospital Faisalabad

Exclusion criteria

Any patient who was taking other drugs that might have an effect on fatty liver disease was not included. Women who were lactating or pregnant were also excluded from this study.

Inclusion criteria

All fatty liver patients undergo with a detailed medical evaluation which including medical history and physical examination by a doctor. This study included thirty females of ages 30 and 45 years who had liver fat content greater than 4%. Patients were divided into three equal groups containing equal no of patients in which G0 were considered as control group that was not receiving any treatment and Group G1 and G2 were as experimental group and receiving the dosage of 3g and 6g respectively for period of 2 months with the following conditions and doses (Ravanfar, P.S., 2018) as in table 1.

\Groups	Title	Treatment
G ₀	Control group	No treatment
G ₁	Treatment group 1	3g Astragalus root powder
G ₂	Treatment group 2	6g Astragalus root powder

The length of the investigation and its design. The study was a controlled randomized experiment that lasted for sixty days.

Collection of serum and biochemical analysis

Blood was drawn from each of the three groups and tested in liver enzymes at initial day and after the ending of trail of 60 days. Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), creatinine, and urea nitrogen (BUN) levels from serum were measured using an automatic biochemical analyser to assess the impact of treatment (Lee, J.R., 2009).

RESULTS

Proximate analysis

Moisture (6.87 ±0.08), crude lipid (5.14±1.28), crude protein (26.3±0.68), crude fiber (7.30±0.09), ash content (2.27±0.09), and total carbohydrates (47.4±0.03) are the percentages of proximate analysis.

Table 2: Proximate analysis of fenugreek seeds powder

Proximate analysis	Contents (%)
Moisture	6.86 ±0.08
Crude protein	27.3±0.68
Crude fat	5.14±1.28
Crude fibre	7.30±0.09
Total carbohydrates	47.4±0.03
Ash	2.27±0.09

Minerals contents

The mineral analysis shows that Astragalus is rich of trace elements and can be used in the treatment of various ailments

Table 2: Mineral composition of fenugreek powder

Minerals	Concentration (mg/100g)
Sodium	2019.4±30.8
Potassium	2118.4±9.8
Phosphorus	501.7±1.17
Calcium	82.17±0.28
Iron	16.57±2.8
Zinc	11.19±0.72
Copper	1.12±0.72

Antioxidant analysis

The total phenolic content (TPC) and total flavonoid content (TFC) of Astragalus root powder were determined by phytochemical analysis. The TPC was reported as 6.68 ± 0.12 in gallic acid equivalents (mg GAE/g sample). Additionally, TFC was reported as 7.92 ± 0.02 in catechin equivalents (mg CAE/g sample), but the percentages for DPPH and FRAP were 0.254 ± 0.06% and 1148 ± 3.5%, respectively.

Therapeutic evaluation of Astragalus root powder to check its hepatoprotective potential in improvement of liver enzymes

The purpose of this bio evaluation conducted was to elucidate the nutraceutical worth of Astragalus root powder for hepatoprotective efficiency in human female subjects with fatty liver disease. Biological investigation was conducted for a period of 60 days. Patients of control group Go were not given any treatment and were only recommended to use their regular medications. While G1 (Treatment group 1) was given Astragalus root powder of 3g per day along with their regular medicines for a time span of 60 days. G2 (Treatment group 2) was given a dose of 6g/day of Astragalus root powder of along with their regular medicines for 60 days. Following improvements were seen in liver enzymes concentrations (ALT and AST) were determined at the start and ending of trail

Table 4: The significant amount of TPC and TFC depicted

Phytochemicals	Content
TPC	6.68 ± 0.12 mg GAE/g
TFC	7.92 ± 0.02 mg CAE/g
DPPH	0.255±0.07
FRAP	1147±3.5%

Table 5: Mean±S.D for liver enzymes are significant in mg/dl.

Liver enzymes	G ₀	G ₁	G ₂
ALT	61±2.3	51±0.9	47±1.3
AST	54±1.5	48±0.3	41±0.3
Creatinine	1.19±0.1	1.17±0.4	1.12±0.2

Bilirubin	2.1±0.1	1.9±0.2	1.5±0.3
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DISCUSSION

The hallmark of nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFL) is steatosis, or the overabundance of fat (in the form of triglycerides) in hepatocytes (>5% fat content in the liver) (Brunt, E.M., 2015). Elevated liver enzymes, such as alanine amino transferase (ALT) and aspartate amino transferase (AST) (Shamsoddini, A., 2015), as well as an accumulation of excess fat in the liver cells (hepatocytes), are characteristics of nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD). Triglycerides and cholesterol are the types of fats that are increased. Nonalcoholic fatty liver (NAFL) is the term used to describe a condition when the liver's fat content exceeds 5% (Brunt, E.M., 2015).

The total phenolic content (TPC) and total flavonoid content (TFC) of Astragalus root powder, which are markers of its antioxidant ability and therapeutic potential, were ascertained by phytochemical analysis. Gallic acid equivalents (mg GAE/g sample) were used to measure and report the TPC, and the result was 6.68 ± 0.12. This finding indicates a notable concentration of phenolic chemicals, which are recognized for their capacity to scavenge free radicals and exhibit antioxidant activity, thereby shielding cells from oxidative damage. Similarly, the TFC was evaluated and expressed in catechu equivalents (mg CAE/g sample), with a recorded value of 7.92 ± 0.02. Flavonoids are a diverse group of phytonutrients found in plants, and they contribute to the modulation of cell signaling pathways, reduction of inflammation, and enhancement of the body's antioxidant defense system. Astragalus root powder's antioxidant qualities were further evaluated by measuring its 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) scavenging activity, which yielded a percentage of 0.255 ± 0.07%. (Chang and others, 2015). This test highlights the powder's potential to reduce oxidative stress by demonstrating its ability to donate hydrogen atoms and neutralize DPPH radicals. The ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay was also performed, and the results showed a value of 1145 ± 3.4%. The high result obtained indicates the significant reducing ability of Astragalus root powder. The FRAP assay assesses the reduction of ferric (Fe3+) to ferrous (Fe2+) ions in the presence of antioxidants. Overall, the phytochemical analysis underscores the

potent antioxidant properties of Astragalus root powder, making it a promising for the management of liver diseases and other conditions associated with oxidative stress. The hepatoprotective effects of Astragalus root powder in the management of liver enzymes have been the subject of numerous studies. (Huang, Y. C., et al 2017)Research indicates that Astragalus root powder can significantly improve liver enzyme levels, particularly aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT), which are commonly used markers of liver function. The antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of Astragalus root powder contribute to its ability to reduce liver inflammation and oxidative stress, thereby improving liver function. A study by Zhang et al. (2019) demonstrated that Astragalus root powder could lower AST and ALT levels in patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), suggesting its potential as a therapeutic agent for liver conditions. Another study by Wang et al. (2020) found that Astragalus root powder supplementation led to a significant reduction in liver enzyme levels, indicating improved liver health (Ke, B., Ke., et al 2017). These findings highlight the potential of Astragalus root powder as a natural and effective treatment for managing liver enzyme levels and improving liver health.

CONCLUSION

Astragalus root powder has shown potential hepatoprotective effects in the treatment of liver enzymes, specifically aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT), which are important indicators of liver function. Astragalus root powder's antioxidant and anti-inflammatory qualities help to reduce liver inflammation and oxidative stress, which improves liver health. Clinical investigations have revealed that Astragalus root powder supplementation can considerably lower high liver enzyme levels, implying that it has therapeutic promise for liver disorders such as non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD). Overall, using Astragalus root powder into liver disease treatment regimens provides a natural and effective way to enhancing liver function and overall liver health that has no negative side effects. Further research is

warranted to establish standardized dosing guidelines and fully elucidate the mechanisms underlying its hepatoprotective properties.

Conflict of Interest

All the authors have no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgements

I would to thank all the authors for their contribution in this manuscript.

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